

Lagrangians with Redundancy

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 16, 2021

In (1), the following Lagrangian is presented: $L = \frac{m}{2} v^2 + U(x)mv - U(x)U(x)$ where v is velocity. The equations of motion of this Lagrangian are identical to those of the simpler $L_1 = \frac{m}{2} v^2 - U(x)$. We argue in this note, that given a simple L_1 , one may be able to construct a more complicated one such that $O[L_2] = H_1 O[L_1]$. Here H_1 is the Hamiltonian associated with L_1 and is a constant, namely energy. $O L = \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dL}{dv} - \frac{dL}{dx}$.

As a result, we argue one must be careful in interpreting Lagrangians. The form $L=T-V$ is often quoted, but one wishes $V(x)$ to be a physical potential which delivers momentum changing hits to a particle. This is particularly important when considering quantum mechanics for which we argue $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$, the $\exp(ikx)$ being virtual photon hits. One may take the Fourier transform of any function, but not any function represents virtual photon hits, so one must take care. For L_2 , $U(x)U(x)$ is the purely spatial potential piece, but it is $U(x)$, as seen from the equations of motion, which delivers momentum changes. The equations of motion may give an indication of a simple constant (say energy) and show explicitly what "potential function" changes v , the velocity.

Unusual Lagrangian

The following unusual Lagrangian is presented in (1):

$$L = \frac{m}{2} v^2 + U(x)mv - U(x)U(x) \quad ((1))$$

$p = \frac{dL}{dv} = mv + 2mUv$ and the Lagrange equations are:

$$\frac{d}{dt} [mv + 2mUv] + 2m v \frac{dU}{dx} - mv \frac{dU}{dx} + 2U \frac{dU}{dx} = 0$$

$$2m \frac{d}{dt} [\frac{m}{2} v^2 + U] + \frac{dU}{dx} [2mv + 2U] = 0$$

$$mv + U \text{ is not zero everywhere so } 2m \frac{d}{dt} [\frac{m}{2} v^2 + U] + \frac{dU}{dx} [2mv + 2U] = 0 \quad ((2))$$

It may be seen that $\frac{m}{2} v^2 + U = \text{constant}$ from ((2)). In fact, a simpler Lagrangian: $L_1 = \frac{m}{2} v^2 - U$ yields ((2)) and $H_1 = \frac{m}{2} v^2 + U$ is its Hamiltonian. The Hamiltonian of L_2 is H_1^2 or energy squared.

Creating a More Complicated Lagrangian from a Simple One

From the above section, one may see it is possible to take a simple Lagrangian and multiply it by E (energy) which is its Hamiltonian. If $O L = \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dL}{dv} - \frac{dL}{dx}$, then:

$$O L_2 = H O L_1 \quad ((4))$$

where H_1 is the Hamiltonian of L_1 . For the simple case $m/2 v^2 + U$, it is a constant namely energy. It may be seen how L_2 from ((1)) fits into this scheme.

$$L_2 = m/2 v^2 + U + 2U L_1 \quad ((5))$$

The form of L_1 is known by writing the Lagrange equations for L_2 and noticing they follow from the simpler L_1 .

$$O[2UL_1] = -2dU/dx L_1 + 2 dU/dx v dL_1/dv + 2U O[L_1] \quad ((6))$$

Thus, one needs a function $b(x)$ such that:

$$Ob(x) - 2dU/dx L_1 + 2 dU/dx v dL_1/dv = 2 m/2 v^2 O[L_1] \quad ((7)) \quad \text{or}$$

From ((5)), $b(x) = m/2 v^2 + U$ where $O[b] = mv dv/dt - 2UdU/dx$ so the right hand side of ((7)) is indeed:

$$2(mv/2) (mdv/dt + dU/dx) \text{ or } 2 (m/2v^2) O[L_1]$$

$$\text{So } O[2UL_1] = 2H_1 O[L_1] \text{ where } H_1 = m/2 v^2 + U$$

Thus, one may take a simple Lagrangian and its Hamiltonian, which is a constant (i.e. energy), and construct a more complicated Lagrangian yielding the same classical equations of motion. Given that $H_1 = E$, the full solution to the equations of motion of $O[L_2]$ are $O[L_1]$.

Physical Implications

Classical equations of motion are physical observables, at least in the classical region. Usually, the Lagrangian is given by $L = T - V$. One may ask whether $V(x)$, the potential, is simply a mathematical function. According to Newton's law, $-dV(x)/dx$ potential is equal to dp/dt . Thus, there seems to be a physical interpretation of a suitable potential. We argue this is carried into quantum mechanics where $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ with $\exp(ikx)$ representing k momentum hits by virtual photons etc. One may write a mathematical "potential" or function as a Fourier series, but one must ensure that it really corresponds to virtual photons, for $\exp(ikx)$ to have physical meaning.

For the complicated Lagrangian L_2 ((1)), one may add and subtract $m/2 v^2$. Then, the "potential" is:

$$U - m(U-1/2)v^2 \quad ((8))$$

This might be interpreted as a regular spatial potential U and a velocity dependent potential $m(U-1/2)v^2$. U could be called $V(x)$. The problem with such a picture physically is that it does not

correspond to the Lagrangian equations of motion in which $U(x)$ is responsible for accelerating $v(x)$, the velocity. It is possible to have other velocity dependent potential which do not accelerate the particle, but UU in ((8)) is not the physical potential responsible for acceleration. Thus, one must treat $L2$ with caution. It yields the equations of motion, but these same equations point to a simpler $L1$ and its corresponding $H1$ (Hamiltonian). These, it seems, should be used to construct a Schrodinger equation and not $L2$ and $H2$. Integrating the equations of motion leads to a constant which corresponds to $H1$, not $H2$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is possible to have a simple Lagrangian $L1$ which yields equations of motions. The Hamiltonian $H1$ of $L1$ matches the constant which follows from integrating the equations of motion.

It is possible to take $L1$ and construct a more complicated Lagrangian $L2$ such that: $O[L2] = H1 O[L1]$ where $H1=E$. Here $O_L = d/dt dL/dv - dL/dx$. Thus, there seems to be redundancy in $L2$. Its Hamiltonian may be shown to be $H1*H1 = EE$ or energy squared and its strictly spatial potential - UU is not the potential responsible for accelerating the particle. Thus, $L2$ seems to be a mathematical construct and we argue that its Hamiltonian $H2$ should not be used to construct a Schrodinger equation (unless one may find a physical reason for doing so).

Here we use: $L1 = m/2 v^2 - U$ and $L2 = mmv^2/2 + mUv - UU$.

Given a Lagrangian which is usually of the form $T-V$, one may erroneously consider a purely spatial term to be a physical potential. We argue that a classical potential $V(x)$ may be written as $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ in quantum mechanics with $\exp(ikx)$ represent k momentum hits from virtual photons. Thus, a purely spatial potential is associated directly with momentum changes. The equations of motion show that $mdv/dt = -dU/dx$ so U is the physical potential delivering momentum hits and not UU .

References

1. Zhao, L. Strange Lagrangian Systems and Statistical Mechanics (2013)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1305.6863.pdf>